

Batch Monitoring Dashboards

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Project Specification

The IT Platform and Engineering Systems group at CERN is running a large batch and grid services used by researchers around the world for processing the data of the LHC experiments and other projects. In order to ensure a successful backbone for the data crunching, an infrastructure has been created to collect and display monitoring information about the system. This project is dedicated to extracting and displaying useful information about the batch service with the help of dashboards, which will further improve the understanding and debugging of our system.

Abstract

In most distributed systems dedicated to scientific projects, a very important part of delivering qualitative services is the monitoring layer that runs on top of such infrastructures. The scope of our project was to ensure a successful backbone for the data processing, by providing meaningful dashboards which will help understand, debug and improve CERN's large batch computing service. Therefore, our project was dedicated to developing an infrastructure meant to collect and display monitoring information about the system by the means of Lemon Sensors and Kibana data visualization platform.

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1 Introduction

Nowadays, with the increase of distributed systems especially within large scientific projects, a very important part of delivering quality services has become related to collecting and monitoring state data. It is also the best approach towards a more performant system: knowing in advance the trends of an ever changing infrastructure.

At CERN, this is also the case. One of the most important IT services we are hosting is the batch computing service. It consists of roughly 65,000 CPU cores meant to provide a backbone for the physics events and simulations. It is open to all CERN users and experiments.

Therefore, monitoring the service is extremely important for the success of the data processing. For that, we have an infrastructure specifically designed to collect and display information about the nodes and jobs. From this perspective, the idea behind our project was born: to create dashboards which will help us understand, debug and improve this large service which processes 400,000 jobs per day.

Moreover, with plots and graphs that show different underlying trends, we will be able to consult the current state of the batch system, to predict issues and ensure maximum efficiency and the best possible service and, also, to provide a means for the users to check the status themselves.

In the remainder of this report we will discuss about the solutions we chose when collecting data (Section 2), what we used to plot data (Section 3) and our results (Section 4).

2 Collecting Data

The first part of our project was designed to collect data from the nodes. For that, we had to decide first between our two main **Elasticsearch** instances and then to use Lemon sensors which collect and output data from LSF. In the following sub-chapters we will discuss these two ideas in more detail.

2.1 IT-Wide vs Group-Wide

In order to display information about the state of the batch service, we use **Elasticsearch**, which is a distributed, highly available and scalable search server based on Lucene. It provides real-time search and analytic capabilities.

A central, general-purpose **Elasticsearch** instance is available for the whole IT Department. In addition, we have set up in our group, our own instance for more specific needs. We took the opportunity to decide which of the two instances we wanted to invest developing sensors and dashboards for. On the one hand, the group-wide instance is flexible and easy to use, but its security and maintenance are the responsibility of the group. On

the other hand, the IT-wide instance imposes constraints and it is not ours to run. We decided to work with the IT-Wide instance.

2.2 Lemon Sensors

Lemon is a server/client based monitoring system. A Lemon agent collects data by communicating with its Lemon sensors running on a batch monitoring node we have set up for the purpose of the project. These sensors are able to measure a given set of metrics.

The sensor we created was in charge of collecting data about LSF jobs running on our batch system. It has 14 fields that display information about the jobs such as:

- user
- sensorversion
- startTime
- submitTime
- endTime
- queue
- chargedSAAP
- cpuFactor
- cpuTime
- exitInfo
- fromHost
- numProcessors
- status
- numExHosts

As we have stated before, we chose to use the IT-wide **Elasticsearch** instance, which imposed some constraints regarding the amount of data we could supply per hour. The problem was that our sensor needed to collect 300,000 job information samples per hour.

This was indeed a problem which we solved by grouping data by: *user*, *queue*, *charged-SAAP*, *exitInfo*, *status* and *numProcessors*. Our Python script managed to reduce the amount of data from our initial 300k to roughly 500 samples per hour.

3 Plotting Data

The most interesting part of our project was to show this information in plots and graphs. For that, we developed an in-house tool to more easily generate **Kibana** dashboards.

3.1 Kibana

Kibana is an open source data visualization plugin for **Elasticsearch**. It is capable of offering a wide variety of graphical representations on top of the content provided by the **Elasticsearch** clusters. With it, users can create plots (bar, line and scatter), pie charts and even maps on top of large volumes of data.

Created to work with **Elasticsearch**, **Kibana** gives shape to any kind of data. It also benefits from **Elasticsearch**'s powerful search and analytic capabilities. Our dashboards were created using **Kibana**'s intuitive interface, but we also developed an in-house tool which aids the dashboard creation process. In the next subsection we will discuss about **Hut** in more detail.

3.2 Hut

Kibana is an easy to use and powerful real-time visualization platform which works on top of **Elasticsearch** to provide meaning to large amounts of data. The only downside is that, being purely json, it can become troublesome to rapidly change or alter the schema of a dashboard especially when your goal is to add many similar features. This is the reason we developed a tool called **Hut** which speeds up the process.

Hut is a Python-based program which uses the Mako Template library to generate fully functioning dashboards. It can be used with the following command:

```
./hut <template_dashboard_file> <data_YAML_file> <output_dashboard_file>
```

As you can see, the user has to provide a template file which is similar to a **Kibana** json file, but which also has Mako templating code where you want to generate json data using information from the YAML file provided as a second argument. An example can be seen in the next code snippets.

Listing 1: Template File

```
"list": {
<% ok = 0 %>
% for id in range(len(rows)):
    <% ok = ok + 1 %>
    "${id}": {
        "enable" : true ,
        "pin" : ${rows[id]['pin']},
```

```

        "color" : "${rows[id]['color']}" ,
        "alias" : "",
        "query" : "${rows[id]['query']}" ,
        "type" : "lucene" ,
        "id" : ${id}
    }
% if ok < len(rows):
    ,
% endif
% endfor
}

```

The first snippet can be found in Listing 1 and it shows Mako templating at work: the output json file will be generated by replacing the variables with their respective values.

The second snippet from Listing 2 shows where the data is taken from: the *data.yaml* file. For each of the templates used to generate dashboards, the user can provide a set of values that will populate the output file.

Listing 2: Data YAML File

```

lsfqueues.ams.template.json:
- color: "#1a331d"
  pin: 'false'
  query: "@message.queue_name=\\\\"ams1nd\\\\"""
- color: "#003ad9"
  pin: 'false'
  query: "@message.queue_name=\\\\"amsmd\\\\"""
- color: "#f23dce"
  pin: 'false'
  query: "@message.queue_name=\\\\"amsprod\\\\"""
- color: "#e24d42"
  pin: 'true'
  query: "*"

```

4 Results

Our final dashboards use both the Lemon sensor we have worked on and the hut tool we developed here. Our first example can be seen in Figure 4.1.

One of our first dashboards was created using **Hut** and it started from an already existing dashboard called LSF Queues. It was a way for us to see our tool in action: we needed a roughly large number of queries to display in the Running vs Pending plot and hut helped us with generating the code for it.

Figure 4.1: LSF Queues

After this first attempt, we wanted to generate dashboards for the LSF jobs and for the data our freshly created Lemon sensor was generating. An example dashboard can be seen in Figure 4.2 where Jobs Statuses are plotted for the total number of jobs, for a chosen user and for a chosen group.

In Figure 4.3 a plot of Job Timings can be seen: here, for a given user and group, we can see the average job duration for a certain period of time. Moreover, we also plotted the average for the total number of jobs.

In Figure 4.4 the Job Resources dashboard is visible. Here, we wanted to see how resources (mainly number of processors) are distributed throughout the LSF jobs. For instance, we

Figure 4.2: Job Statuses

Figure 4.3: Job Timings

can conclude from both the pie chart, the table and the graph, that most submitted jobs use 1 processor. Also, the next most popular option is with 4 cores and 8 cores.

5 Conclusions

As we have seen throughout this report, a successful monitoring infrastructure is not an easy task to manage. First of all, you need a good backbone for the collectors, which, in our case, were the Lemon Sensors - dedicated to provide valuable information about the state of the LSF jobs (such as: the submitter's username, the start-submit-end times of

Figure 4.4: Job Resources

the job, the queue name, CPU factor and time, exit information, the number of processors involved and the status of the job).

Secondly, a thorough understanding of the processes involved requires visualization capabilities and for that, we have chosen Kibana which offers visualization such as bar charts, line and scatter plots, histograms, pie charts, and maps.

The challenges we faced were mainly focused on two different aspects of the project: the first one was related to the fact that we chose the IT-Wide Elasticsearch instance which imposed constraints such as the number of samples per hour. We tackled this situation by grouping data such that we have managed to reduce the amount of data from around 300,000 samples to around 500 samples per hour.

The other challenge we had was to reduce the amount of time spent on creating a dashboard. Because Kibana is entirely json, if one wants to rapidly change the schema of a dashboard, it has to manually edit the file or use the GUI. That can become tedious and so this is how the idea behind our in-house tool called **Hut** was born. It is a Python-based program which uses the Mako Template library to generate fully functioning dashboards and it was used to create all of the dashboards you have seen so far in this report.

For future work, new metrics can be plotted using both the sensor and **Hut** and in the process understand what weak points our tool has. Also, the data file used for **Hut** can be further improved for future dashboards to a different hierarchy if one wants to provide more complex data structure to their template and need not comply to its present form.